

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

**Deliverable 3.1 Research, innovation
and market watch methodology and
framework**

Public

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1. Summary

Research, innovation and market watch methodology and framework is the first deliverable in Work package three. It consists of six main sections:

- Section one includes an introduction that sets the scene and explains the objectives and content of this deliverable and how the developed methodology orchestrates work package three activities.
- Section two explains the relationship between work packages two and three elaborating on the proposed light Delphi approach to be adopted to prioritize practitioners' technical requirements as well as challenges and opportunities and how these contribute to the definition of the research, innovation and market watch baseline.
- Section three explores how the research, innovation and market watch baseline is to be developed by detailing how the systematic desk research should be conducted and what to include in the industry, universities, research facilities and security network surveys and how collected information feeds into the anticipated baseline.
- Section four details how live exercises should be developed including how specific technologies and R&D innovations will be selected and how the scenarios themselves can be and evaluated.
- Section five explains how this methodology is expanded to achieve long term monitoring of improvements and how to take into consideration new research in addition to any products developed throughout the project lifecycle.
- Section six concludes the deliverable and includes a process flow diagram that explains the relationship between activities and deliverables in work package three while highlighting inputs and outputs and the relationship with work package two activities and relevant deliverables.
- Section seven includes proposed questionnaires to compliment activities and methods elaborated in the framework. All proposed questionnaires are included in separate appendices.

2. Introduction

The CYCLOPES project has been introduced to enhance the EU’s ability in counteracting cybercrime by ensuring law enforcement agencies (LEAs) are competitive, innovation-driven and collaborate effectively whilst connecting industry and academia through the simulation of dialogue on pressing security matters threatening the stability of Europe and citizens’ safety.

The CYCLOPES project has multiple objectives. Work package three (WP3) contributes directly to achieving the third objective in CYCLOPES which is “to monitor development of new technologies, research activities and innovations applied to combatting cybercrime”. This shall be facilitated by establishing a bridge between practitioners, academia, and industry to monitor how existing technologies and research and innovation can address the requirements, gaps and challenges identified by practitioners.

The outcome of such collaboration will lead to the identification of current research, development and commercially available solutions or close-to-market products that directly address the challenges identified and can be used by practitioners. Similarly, promising research and development activities currently undertaken will be identified. Also work in WP3 will lead to the identification of critical needs of practitioners which are not currently adequately met and where the opportunities available to address them can be defined.

All this will be achieved through the implementation of three main activities:

- Monitoring and validating LEAs’ requirements
- Conducting market and research horizon scanning to overcome gaps
- Organising joint live exercises to test solutions.

The medium term anticipated impact for WP3 is “common understanding of innovation potential, more widely accepted understanding, expression of common innovation and standardisation needs among practitioners in the same discipline”.

Figure 1 below depicts the relationship between WP3 main activities, CYCLOPES relevant objective and KPIs and the anticipated impact.

Figure 1 Relationship between WP3 main activities and CYCLOPES’s relevant objective, KPIs and impact

D3.1 Research, innovation and market watch methodology and framework is the first deliverable in WP3. Its objective is to define the methodology for scanning the market and research domain, looking for ready and forthcoming solutions, which answer the identified gaps and requirements of LEAs regarding cybercrime. This methodology will:

- Describe how the outcomes of work package two (WP2) workshops define the requirements, specific gaps and opportunities which feed into the market-watch.
- Clarify how relevant research, innovation and market solutions are to be identified and classified.
- Explain how specific research / technologies will be selected for the live exercise scenarios and how the scenarios themselves can be developed and evaluated.
- Propose a mechanism for supporting the long-term monitoring of improvements and new research in addition to any products developed throughout the life of the project.

3. CYCLOPES market watch and WP2

WP2 is considered the engine of the project as it enables, through practitioners' workshops, the identification of gaps and requirements as well as the definition of authorities' capabilities with regard to combating cybercrime. CYCLOPES, as part of WP3 methodology, will implement a light Delphi process, while considering horizon scanning principles to validate and prioritise the most pertinent technology and research challenges for LEAs identified in collaboration with WP2.

3.1. Themes Definition

The first step will be defining the themes of practitioners' workshops for the upcoming 12 months. This shall take place through a designated team of experts from the CYCLOPES consortium who will review the latest trends and threats within the cybercrime domain and choose the most applicable themes. Identified themes are to be classified under three main topics:

- digital forensics;
- cybercrime affecting people;
- cybercrime affecting systems.

3.2. LEAs' questionnaires

The second step will be defining technological challenges, requirements and opportunities. *Horizon scanning*¹ will be adopted along with a *light Delphi approach* to validate and prioritise identified challenges and requirements. The light Delphi approach will consist of two data collection cycles from LEA experts. This approach is adopted since Delphi is an interactive focusing method that depends on the feedback of a panel of experts² and will enable the creation of robust models of challenges and potential solutions. Similar to the followed approach in the Security Research Community of Users DG Home project, *Disaggregative Policy Delphi* approach (Tapio, 2003)³ is selected since it does not assume, nor necessarily

¹ Horizon scanning is defined by Jon Day as a "systematic examination of information to identify potential threats, risks, emerging issues and opportunities". Gov.uk website

² Bernice B. Brown (1968). "Delphi Process: A Methodology Used for the Elicitation of Opinions of Experts.": An earlier paper published by RAND (Document No: P-3925, 1968, 15 pages)

³ Tapio, P. (2003). Disaggregative Policy Delphi: Using cluster analysis as a tool for systematic scenario formation. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 70(1), 83-101

seek, consensus on future scenarios especially with regard to social and technological change. This approach rather focuses on identifying clusters of similar opinions and perspectives and accordingly serves an exploratory purpose, collecting research areas, gaps and challenges in a bottom-up manner to obtain a broad, comprehensive foundation for the market watch.⁴

To ensure that information about technological challenges, opportunities, requirements and tools and technologies that feeds into the research and market watch is comprehensive and fit-for purpose, data collection is conducted in two phases:

- **Phase 1:** knowledge elicitation. This is the information elicited from LEAs' experts through questionnaires prior to practitioners' workshops. During this phase, experts will be asked to:
 - Identify the main technologies/tools that are being *currently used or researched and developed* within their area of specialty/ domain and focusing on the identified theme(s).
 - Identify and rank up to five main *technological and R&D challenges* the respective agency is currently encountering with regard to the identified theme(s).
 - Identify and rank up to five main technological requirements related to the usage of technologies and tools in their domain with regard to identified themes(s).
 - Identify and rank up to five main *opportunities* related to the usage of future technologies and tools in their domain including innovations being researched and developed with regard to the identified theme (s).
 - Detail any future needs their agency anticipates with regard to dark web and quantum computing.

Appendix I includes a proposed of LEA's questionnaire pre practitioners' workshops.

- **Phase 2:** Simplified validation and selection. This phase is related to the validation and ranking of technological and R&D challenges, requirements and opportunities during the practitioners' workshops after elicited knowledge from the first phase is shared through practitioners' presentations. After presentations, during 30-60 minutes dedicated to WP3 within practitioners' workshops, experts will be asked again to:
 - Identify and rank technological and R&D challenges that are the most pertinent regarding the identified theme.
 - Identify and rank the technological requirements that are most pertinent regarding the identified theme.
 - Identify and rank technological and R&D opportunities that are the most pertinent regarding the identified theme.
 - Identify and rank future needs related to dark web and quantum computing.

The ranking format was chosen to collect quantifiable insights into which specific challenges, technological requirements and opportunities are seen as the most pertinent. An average ranking is calculated for each answer choice, allowing CYLOPES researchers during the analysis phase to evaluate the most preferred answer choice by participants.

Appendix II includes a proposed LEA's questionnaire during practitioners' workshops.

⁴ Reference: CoU2.0/DG HOME. Elicitation of Future Research Needs and Direction for the FCT EU Research Program. Findings of Phase 1: Knowledge Elicitation. November 2020.

4. Research, innovation and market watch baseline definition

Identified themes and relevant prioritised technological and R&D challenges, opportunities and requirements form the foundation for developing the research and market watch baseline. Technological developments and trends and R&D initiatives related to identified themes, challenges, requirements and opportunities mapped to specific cybercrimes affecting people and systems and digital forensics are to be scanned through:

- Systematic desk research;
- Industry, universities and research centres, CYCLOPES network and cyber-security EU and International Organisations surveys.

These two techniques compliment each other and are to run in parallel to WP2 activities.

4.1. Systematic desk research (SDR)

Systematic desk research is to be conducted in order to identify and evaluate technologies and research initiatives relevant to selected themes and relevant prioritised challenges, opportunities and requirements. SDR will also lead to the identification of any gaps in existing technologies and R&D initiatives and suggest areas for further investigation providing a framework to new research activities.

The purpose of the review is to gather knowledge on “available” tools and solutions to counter cybercrime according to selected themes as well as knowledge of technologies under “research and development” in the same domain. Existing EU, national and regional technologies and R&D initiatives are to be researched to establish synergies where possible. Also tools and solutions deployed and adopted outside the EU region are to be considered for benchmarking purposes and to establish evidence.

This systematic desk research is intended to feed into the design and development of the research, innovation and market watch (RIMWA) while taking into consideration the requirements of LEAs. In order to achieve this, and to ensure the collection of all relevant information, several research questions are to be created. These questions will help to ensure that the RIMWA is comprehensive in its nature, whilst providing an in-depth analysis into the existing research, innovation and market watch technological tools and solutions that target cybercrime and digital forensic in selected themes. Two main research questions are:

- What are the existing technological tools and solutions used with regard to the identified theme?
- What are the technological R&D initiatives under development with regard to identified theme?

Resources to be searched in order to identify and collect relevant information are to include, yet not limited to: electronic databases, websites, journals as well as reports from CYCLOPES beneficiaries, networks and stakeholders and EU and International Organisations identified in WP5 (e.g., ENLETS, ENFSI, i-LEAD, i-LeaNet, EU-HYBNET and i-ProcureNet, EC, EC3, Europol’s Innovation Hub, Interpol, ENISA, {SPARTA, ECHO, CONCORDIA - CyberSec4Europe}, CLAIR, EOS).

As the systematic desk research progresses, a database of tools, solution and R&D initiatives is to be developed.

Full text searches will be run on each of the resources outlined. The following are examples of search strings to be run on electronic resources. These may be revised based on identified challenges, opportunities and requirements in WP2.

- (Tool OR Solution) AND (“Cybercrime” OR “Digital Forensics”) AND (*Selected Theme*) AND (*Identified Challenge OR Identified Requirement OR Identified Opportunity*) AND (Europe).
- (Tool OR Solution) AND (“Cybercrime” OR “Digital Forensics”) AND (*Selected Theme*) AND (*Identified Challenge or Identified Requirement or Identified Opportunity*) AND (Global OR International Or Worldwide).

Only relevant material (reports, papers, articles and studies) are to be accepted into the systematic desk research and a selection process is to be followed to test and verify the consistency of the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criterion is reports, studies, article and technical papers containing only the search terms, or synonyms of search terms. The exclusion criterion is reports, papers, articles and studies in languages other than English or issued more than ten years ago.

Reports, studies, articles and technical papers found in the search are to be assessed for their suitability based upon analysis of their content. Clearly irrelevant material is to be excluded. This is done to ensure that the report, study, article or paper in question definitely contains information that is relevant to the desk research being performed, as well as data that can be extracted for later analysis. Each material (report, study, article or paper) it to be assessed to ensure that a particular identified tool, solution of initiative will make a valuable contribution to the systematic desk research.

It is expected that lots of information will be collected during the course of the systematic desk research. The reference of each material that is deemed suitable for inclusion it to be entered into a (Reference Manager) along with the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and a short note consisting of the name and short description of the identified tool, solution or initiative is to be included.

The full texts of accepted publications/material are to be stored. The following information is to be extracted from accepted studies:

- Type (e.g. technical report, journal paper, conference paper etc.)
- Date of publication.
- Listing of identified tools, solutions and/or R&D initiatives.
- Short description of identified tools, solutions and/or initiatives.

Excel and/or NVIVO are to be used for the management of the screening and data extraction stages of the SDR process.

4.2. Industry, university, research facilities and security network surveys

In addition to systematic desk research, and to formulate a robust research and market watch, three types of surveys are to be conducted to identify existing or researched tools and solutions to prevent, detect, mitigate, or investigate an existing or future cybercrime including digital forensics tools and solutions. The surveys are to target:

- *Industry* to identify existing tools and solutions relevant to identified themes and to gauge interest in taking part of live exercises by demonstrating solution and developing scenarios.
- *Universities and research agencies* to identify relevant research initiatives and researched technologies and to gauge interest in taking part of live exercises.
- *Networks and relevant stakeholders survey* to identify existing tools and solutions, research initiatives and researched technologies. This survey shall target cyber-security and EU and

International Organisations identified in WP5 such as ENLETS, ENFSI, i-LEAD, i-LeaNet, EU-HYBNET and i-ProcureNet, EC, EC3, Europol's Innovation Hub, Interpol, ENISA, SPARTA, ECHO, CONCORDIA - CyberSec4Europe, CLAIR and EOS.

4.2.1. Industry survey

Main technology providers in the domain of cyber-security solutions and digital forensics in Europe and Internationally are to be approached to fill a questionnaire and provide information, based on the identified needs of practitioners, about the tools / solutions they already offer, recommend or are currently under development. Industry players are to be asked a set of questions that shall form the base for how the identified research, innovation and market solutions are *classified*. The proposed questions are related to:

- Identifying and recommending *relevant* existing tools and solutions and technologies under research and development.
- Providing a short description of identified technologies including their scope and how and in what way they address the identified themes.
- Selecting the category of identified technologies. This includes yet not limited to:
 - Cyber security
 - Digital forensics
 - Threat intelligence
 - Case management.
- Selecting the features of identified technologies. This includes⁵:
 - AI Machine learning
 - Activity Dashboard
 - Alerts / Notifications
 - Application security
 - Anomaly / Malware Detection
 - Behavioural analysis
 - Continuous monitoring
 - Data Visualization
 - Endpoint Protection or Endpoint Detection and Response
 - Event Analysis
 - Fraud Detection
 - Incident Management (reporting)
 - IOC verification
 - Investigation Management
 - Monitoring
 - Network Monitoring
 - Network provisioning
 - Prioritization
 - Real time data
 - Remediation Management
 - Reporting / Analytics
 - Root cause analysis
 - Search / Filter
 - Server Monitoring

⁵ This is an extensive list of features for the different tools and solutions that can be identified under the four categories mentioned in the previous question. This list may be revised during the project noting participants' feedbacks and the identification of new features.

- Task Management
- Threat Intelligence
- Threat Response
- Tokenization
- Vulnerability scanning
- Web-application security
- Whitelisting / blacklisting
- Others
- Selecting the deployment options of identified technologies. This includes:
 - Cloud SaaS, Web based
 - Desktop Mac
 - Desktop Windows
 - Desktop Linux
 - On-Promise Windows
 - On-Promise Linux
 - Desktop Chromebook
 - Mobile Android
 - Mobile iPhone (iOS)
 - Tablet iPad (iPadOS)
 - Others
- Selecting the availability options of identified technologies. This could be:
 - Commercial
 - Open source
 - Non-commercial Intellectual Property (this covers technologies originally developed by a university, research facility, or national laboratory, that are not available yet for purchase, licensing, or via opensource markets.)
- Selecting the pricing option for identified technologies.
 - Free
 - Free Trial
 - Monthly subscription
 - Annual Subscription
 - One time license
 - Other (please specify, example non-commercial Intellectual Property (IP))
- For non-commercial IP, selecting:
 - The technology readiness level (TRL)⁶. This includes:
 - Level 1 – Basic principles observed
 - Level 2 – Technology concept formulated
 - Level 3 – Experimental proof of concept
 - Level 4 – Technology validated in lab
 - Level 5 – Technology validated in relevant environment
 - Level 6 – Technology demonstrated in relevant environment
 - Level 7 – System prototype demonstration in operational environment
 - Level 8 – System complete and qualified
 - Level 9 – Actual system proven in operational environment

⁶ ["Technology readiness levels \(TRL\): Extract from Part 19 - Commission Decision C\(2014\)4995" \(PDF\)](#). ec.europa.eu. 2014. Retrieved 21 September 2021. Material was copied from this source, which is available under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](#)

- The technology development timelines⁷:
 - 6 – 12 months
 - 1 – 2 years
 - 2-5 years
- Expressing the willingness to demonstrate identified technologies and/or participate in live exercises.

Appendix III includes a proposed industry questionnaire.

4.2.2. Universities and research facilities survey

Universities and research facilities that have dedicated faculties or departments specialising in cyber-security solutions and/or digital forensics in Europe are to be approached to fill a questionnaire and provide information about the tools / solutions that they are researching and developing. They are to be asked a set of questions that shall form the base for how the identified researched innovations are classified in the watch. The proposed questions are related to:

- Identifying and recommending relevant existing tools and solutions and technologies under research and development.
- Providing a short description of researched and/or developed technologies including their scope and how and in what way they address the identified themes.
- Selecting the category of identified technologies (using the same list of categories included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the features of identified technologies (using the same list of features included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the deployment option for identified technologies (using the same list of options included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the technology readiness level of researched and/or developed technologies (using the same list of TRL included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the technology development timeline of researched and/or developed technologies (using the same options included in the industry survey)
- Exploring interest to demonstrate researched and/or developed technologies and/or participate in live exercises.

Appendix IV includes a proposed universities and research facilities questionnaire.

4.2.3. Security networks and relevant stakeholders' survey

Networks and relevant stakeholders are to be approached to fill a questionnaire and provide information, based on the identified needs of practitioners, about existing tools / solutions they recommend or are currently under research and development. This survey shall target cyber-security and EU and International Organisations identified in WP5 such as ENLETS, ENFSI, i-LEAD, i-LeaNet, EU-HYBNET and i-ProcureNet, EC, EC3, Europol's Innovation Hub, Interpol, ENISA, SPARTA, ECHO, CONCORDIA – CyberSec4Europe, CLAIR and EOS. Similar to industry, universities and research facilities this group is to be asked a set of questions that shall form the base for how the identified research, innovation and market solutions are *classified*. The proposed questions are related to:

⁷ This is the timeframe for a non-commercial IP to become an actual system proven in operational environment.

- Identifying and recommending *relevant* existing tools and solutions and technologies under research and development.
- Providing a short description of existing, researched and/or developed technologies including their scope and how and in what way they address the identified themes.
- Defining the category of identified technologies (using the same list of categories included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the features of identified technologies (using the same list of features included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the deployment option for identified technologies (using the same list of options included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the pricing option for identified technologies (using the same list of pricing options included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the availability mode for identified technologies (using the modes included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the technology readiness level of identified technologies (using the same list of TRL included in the industry survey)
- Selecting the technology development timeline of researched and/or developed technologies (using the same options included in the industry survey)
- Exploring interest to demonstrate identified technologies and/or participate in live exercises.

Appendix V includes a proposed security networks and relevant stakeholders' questionnaire.

5. Mapping practitioners' challenges, opportunities and requirements with research, innovation and market watch data

Information gathered from LEAs pre and during workshops will provide the reference for identifying prioritised technical challenges, opportunities and requirement of LEA communities taking into consideration the different roles participants play: cybercrime investigators, digital forensics expert, first responders (CSIRT community), etc. CYCLOPES team of experts will map prioritised technical requirements with the identified research and technology innovations resulting from systematic desk research and industry, universities, research facilities, security networks and CYCLOPES' stakeholders' surveys.

Considering each theme and the identified relevant challenges, requirements and opportunities from the WP2 workshops, CYCLOPES team of experts will research, collate and analyse existing solutions and relevant research and innovation at each readiness level to understand:

- Existing products / services that can address identified requirements
- High-TRL research that with *seed investment* could be transformed into a market product,
- Low to mid TRL promising research that could address the requirements
- Requirements that are not directly addressed by any known product or research direction that highlight a gap in the research landscape.

Although the research, innovation and market watch is intended to be comprehensive, a scoring system will be used to reflect to what extent identified research and innovations are

capable to meet and respond to practitioners' requirements and prioritised technical needs. This is vital as there would be *differences* in prioritised requirements and impact among LEAs across countries as well differences in TRL and investment abilities in innovations under R&D.

Virtual meetings are to be conducted with practitioners to present research outcomes and to score identified technologies and innovations under R&D. Scores will take into consideration four main factors:

- *Plausibility* of identified technologies and R&D innovations.
- *Impact* of identified technologies and R&D innovations.
- *Availability of funds to invest* in identified technologies and R&D innovations.
- *Technology Readiness Level (TRL)* of researched innovations and technologies under development.

The final research, innovation and market watch (RIMWA) will consist of two main parts:

- **Part one:** Existing Technologies in the Market

This will include all identified existing technologies in the market that respond to practitioners' challenges and meet their requirements. Technologies (including tools and solutions) will be arranged based on the prioritised needs, plausibility, impact and availability of funding. Identified technologies with the highest scores will be listed first. The information in this part will be classified as follows:

- First Level. All technology categories to be displayed. (Cyber Security, Digital Forensics, Case Management... etc)
- Second level. For each category all technologies are to be displayed and ranked based on score. Within each category and per technology the following information is to be displayed:
 - Features
 - Availability (Commercial Vs Open Source)
 - Pricing Option
 - Deployment Option
 - Pricing

- **Part two:** Innovations under R&D

This will include all identified researched technologies and/or technologies that are still under development yet meet practitioners' requirements and identified opportunities. Researched innovations will be arranged based on the prioritised needs, plausibility, impact, technology readiness level and availability of funding. R&D innovations with the highest scores will be listed first. The information in this part will be classified as follows:

- First Level. All R&D innovation categories to be displayed. (Cyber Security, Digital Forensics, Case Management... etc)
- Second level. For each category all R&D innovations are to be displayed and ranked based on score. Within each category and per R&D innovation the following information is to be displayed:
 - Features
 - Technology readiness level
 - Time to market (development timeline)
 - Deployment option (if known)

An annex to be added to include requirements that are not directly addressed by any known product or research direction that highlight a gap in the research landscape.

The final research, innovation and market watch (RIMWA) information is to be included in a repository that can be easily accessed by LEAs who should be able to search for and filter information taking into consideration the parameters mentioned earlier, such technology category, features, availability, deployment option...,etc. LEAs are to be consulted regarding the most desirable format and tool to be used to access the RIMWA's information.

6. Conducting joint live exercises

Live exercises form a cornerstone in WP3. These exercises will enable a direct contact between practitioners, the industry and academia and research agencies while practitioners deploy, test and verify *selected* innovative solutions identified through the scanning activities of WP3. The practical sessions will also provide industry attendees and research agencies with direct feedback from practitioners regarding the way they operate in the field and how the solutions can be adjusted to better suit their needs. Live exercises sessions shall provide an intimate atmosphere and closed environment that is conducive for fruitful discussion between the companies, research facilities and LEAs. Companies and research facilities will be encouraged to consider ideas for collaboration and possible synergies that can combat the practitioners' identified gaps and meet their requirements.

Live exercises are to be organised in suitable facilities prepared for testing and training (including areas used for digital forensics, which mostly require sophisticated tools, computers and software to conduct training and testing). Premises of consortium partners (such as TNO, Swedish Police) as well as external institutions that have expressed their willingness to support the CYCLOPES project will be used. This annual session will be dedicated to a group of around 20-25 practitioners, as well as representatives of industry and research facilities.

Companies and research facilities filling the industry survey are to be asked whether they would like to participate in any future live exercises. CYCLOPES project team of experts will select interested companies and research agencies accordance to the identified technical gaps and needs / requirements of LEAs collected in WP2 workshops.

Annual live exercises will be guided by *scenarios* prepared based on identified practitioners' technical requirements and possibly gaps for the specific year and adapted to technologies provided by industry and research facilities invited for a particular exercise. Practitioners will be divided into groups with tasks distributed between them. The practitioners, following the scenarios, will use the solutions identified and delivered by the companies and research facilities for the joint live exercise event. Short trainings may be conducted part of the live exercises' sessions to familiarize attendees with the novel solutions and methods required to execute the scenario(s).

Specific research / technologies will be selected for the live exercise scenarios based on two factors:

- Company's / research facility's willingness to participate in the sessions.
- The score of technology and R&D innovation obtained while mapping practitioners' technical needs with RIMWA data. The scoring process shall take into consideration prioritised needs, plausibility, impact, technology readiness level and availability of funding.

The three technologies / solutions with the highest score under each theme are to be selected and respective companies and/or research organisations are to be contacted to start working with CYCLOPES project experts on the development of scenarios. Different practitioners' roles are to be taken into consideration when developing scenarios:

- Cybercrime investigators (covering investigation)
- Digital forensics expert (covering investigation)
- First responders (CSIRT) (covering prevention and detection)
- Prosecutors (covering prosecution)

Practitioners who participate in the live exercises' sessions will assess the live exercises activities and how successful each technology performs using a likert rating scale⁸ considering different areas such as the capability of the solution, its interoperability with the working environment of the participants, the maturity of the solution, the usability and user friendliness of the solution and to what extent it meet's the practitioner's requirements as well as his/her organisation's requirements. Appendix VI includes a proposed evaluation form for live exercises.

Figure 2 below summarizes the proposed process flow for conducting the joint live excercises.

⁸ It is proposed to use this psychometric scale to allow participants to specify their level of agreement to statements related to the process of conducting the live exercises and the solutions being tested using five points such as: (1) Clearly unsuitable; (2) Marginal; (3) Acceptable; (4) Good; (5) Excellent.

Figure 2 Joint live exercises process flow

7. Long term monitoring of improvements and new research

While it is significant to identify the status quo in terms of LEA’s requirements and relevant research and innovations existing in the market, it is as well important to introduce a mechanism to support the long-term monitoring of improvements and new research including any products developed throughout the project lifecycle. Therefore, while new themes are introduced every year, the identified technologies *from previous years’ themes* are to be investigated by monitoring their improvements, understanding the progressive state-of-play for innovation, building upon the results from the mapping of existing and forthcoming solutions against the requirements and the joint live exercises, from previous years, and iteratively and

continuously monitoring new and emerging research and products relevant to previous years' themes. To achieve this in a practical approach noting that annual research, innovation and market watch reports are "confidential" and joint live exercises reports are "classified information", CYCLOPES project team of experts will:

- (A) **Repeat and update desk research for past years' themes:** While running the systematic desk research, detailed in section three of this deliverable, for the current year's themes, run a "*parallel*" desk research, following the same methodology, for previous years' themes. Exclude all already identified technologies/solutions and/or R&D initiatives.
- (B) **Updates related to past years' live exercises:** Through systematic desk research, look for any updates and / or recent reports related to identified innovations and research initiatives *presented during the previous years' live exercises*. The two main *additional* research questions are:
 - Are there any updates related to the technological tools and solutions (S1, S2 and S3)⁹ with regard to themes X,Y and Z from previous years?
 - Are there any updates related to the R&D initiatives (R1, R2 and R3)¹⁰ under development with regard to themes X,Y and Z from previous years?
- (C) Send a *specific* short questionnaire only to respective organisations (company, academia, research facility or security network organisation) which already provided input regarding the technology and/or R&D initiative experimented during the live exercises.
 - For technologies and innovations existing in the market, the entity is to be asked if there have been any updates/changes in terms of:
 - Scope
 - Features
 - Availability (Commercial Vs Open Source)
 - Pricing Option
 - Deployment Option
 - For R&D innovations / initiatives, the entity is to be asked if there have been any updates in terms of:
 - Scope
 - Features
 - Availability
 - Pricing Option¹¹
 - Technology readiness level
 - Time to market (development timeline)¹²
 - Deployment option (if known)

This monitoring framework will provide yearly 'innovation updates' on past workshop themes detailing new solutions or research directions (*through the deployment of activity A*). It will also closely monitor the solutions presented in the Joint Live Exercises, (*through the deployment*

⁹ S1, S2 and S3 are the tested tools / solutions during live exercises in previous years.

¹⁰ R1, R2 and R3 are the tested R&D technologies during live exercises in previous years.

¹¹ For R&D technologies which matured and became available in the market.

¹² For R&D technologies which are not yet available in the market.

of activities B and C) to understand how the research or product has developed based on feedback during those sessions to demonstrate the on-going progress of the project.

An additional advantage of this approach is that it enables us to apply new tools that emerge (for example text analytics tools that use NLP for more advanced analysis and that can handle much bigger amounts of documents automatically), and use such tools to uncover updates and trends for previous themes as well as, improve on previous results.

Appendix VII includes a proposed technology and R&D innovation monitoring questionnaire.

8. Conclusion

D3.1 Research, innovation and market watch methodology and framework is the first deliverable in WP3. It describes the process workflow, methods and tools to be used to scan the market and research domain while searching for ready and future solutions, which respond to the identified gaps and requirements of LEAs regarding cybercrime. Figure 2 below summarizes the process flow explained in previous sections while highlighting the inputs and outputs of each activity taking into consideration relevant deliverables in WP2 and WP3.

Figure 3 Methodology process flow, inputs, outputs and relationship with work packages two and three relevant deliverables

Although the proposed framework is intended to be comprehensive, it is to be revisited post implementation annually to ensure incorporating lessons learnt to enhance the proposed methodology and provide a robust framework that can be customised in future projects.

9. Appendices¹³

Appendix I: Practitioners' pre-workshops questionnaire

General Information	
LEA Name:	
Role within the LEA	Specialties / Domains
<input type="checkbox"/> Investigator <input type="checkbox"/> Digital Forensic expert <input type="checkbox"/> First Responder <input type="checkbox"/> Prosecutor <input type="checkbox"/> Others	
* Please specify specialties / domains under selected role(s) and provide <i>if possible</i> a brief description of the activities within your role(s)	
Question 1: What are the main technologies/tools that are being currently <u>used</u> or <u>researched & developed</u> within your area of specialty/ domain and focusing on (THEME X, Y or Z)? Instruction: List items in order of <i>relevance</i> for your role with 1 being most relevant technology/tool. Flag area as: P (Prevention) D(Detection) I(investigation) O(Prosecution) [Note: The main focus here should be tools and technologies that are related to roles. Please feel free to list as many technologies as you want.]	
Relevance	Area* Existing/R&D Main technology /tool used or under R&D in relation to respondent's role and specialty
1	
2	
3	
4	
...	
Question 2: What are the 5 main <u>technological and R&D</u> challenges your agency is currently encountering with regard to (THEME X, Y or Z)? Instruction: Please rank your entries from 1 to 5 with 1 being the most important challenge.	
Rank	Description of challenge
1	
2	
3	

¹³ Legal and ethical guidelines developed as part of work package seven (WP7) are to be followed when conducting all proposed questionnaires. Please note deliverable D7.3 Actionable Ethics and Legal Guidance Document and refer to deliverables D7.1 (Consent Forms) and D7.2(Non-EU-Countries) for required consent forms for proposed questionnaires.

4							
5							
<p>Question 3: What are the 5 main opportunities related to the usage of future technologies and tools in your domain including innovations being researched and developed with regard to (THEME X, Y or Z)? Instruction: Please rank your entries from 1 to 5 with 1 being the most important opportunity.</p>							
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rank</th> <th>Description of opportunity</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Rank	Description of opportunity	1	2	3	4	5
Rank	Description of opportunity						
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
<p>Question 4: What are the 5 main <u>technological requirements</u> of your agency with regard to (THEME X, Y or Z)? Instruction: Please rank your entries from 1 to 5 with 1 being the most important.</p>							
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Rank</th> <th>Description of requirement</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Rank	Description of requirement	1	2	3	4	5
Rank	Description of requirement						
1							
2							
3							
4							
5							
<p>Question 5: What are the anticipated future needs of your agency with regard to dark web and quantum computing [Note: Please feel free to detail as many needs as you want.]</p>							
<p>Future needs related to dark web:</p> <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td>...</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	2	3		...		
1							
2							
3							
...							
<p>Future needs related to quantum computing:</p> <table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td> </td></tr> <tr><td>...</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	2	3		...		
1							
2							
3							
...							

Appendix II: Practitioners' questionnaire during workshops

General Information	
LEA Name:	
Role within the LEA	Specialties / Domains
<input type="checkbox"/> Investigator <input type="checkbox"/> Digital Forensic expert <input type="checkbox"/> First Respondent <input type="checkbox"/> Prosecutor <input type="checkbox"/> Others	
* Please specify specialties / domains under selected role(s) and provide <i>if possible</i> a brief description of the activities within your role(s)	
Which technological and R&D challenges are the most pertinent with regard to (THEME X, Y or Z)?	
Please <i>rank</i> the following challenges from 1: most pertinent to XX: least pertinent. Add any challenges not currently listed under 'Other'.	
<i>(A list that includes all identified challenges from pre-workshop questionnaire)</i>	
Which technological requirements are the most pertinent with regard to (THEME X, Y or Z)?	
Please <i>rank</i> the following areas from 1: most pertinent to XX: least pertinent. Add any requirements not currently listed under 'Other'.	
<i>(A list that includes all identified requirements from pre-workshop questionnaire)</i>	
Which technologies/tools/ technological R&D opportunities are the most pertinent with regard to (THEME X, Y or Z)?	
Please <i>rank</i> the following areas from 1: most pertinent to XX: least pertinent. Add any opportunities not currently listed under 'Other'.	
<i>(A list that includes all identified opportunities from pre-workshop questionnaire)</i>	
Which needs are the most pertinent with regard to the dark web	
Please <i>rank</i> the following areas from 1: most pertinent to XX: least pertinent. Add any needs not currently listed under 'Other'.	
<i>(A list that includes all identified needs from pre-workshop questionnaire)</i>	
Which needs are the most pertinent with regard to quantum computing	
Please <i>rank</i> the following areas from 1: most pertinent to XX: least pertinent. Add any needs not currently listed under 'Other'.	
<i>(A list that includes all identified needs from pre-workshop questionnaire)</i>	

Appendix III: Industry questionnaire

General Information			
<i>Company Name:</i>			
<i>Location:</i>			
<i>Main domains the company focuses on:</i>			
<i>Name of person filling the survey:</i>			
<i>Role within the company:</i>			
<i>E-mail Address:</i>			
<i>Contact number:</i>			
Question 1: What are the <u>technologies/tools</u> that you offer and/or recommend OR you are currently researching and/or developing that focus on (THEME X, Y or Z)?			
Select/ define category: Case Management Cyber Security Digital Forensics Threat Intelligence Other (specify)			
Please provide a short description of technologies including their scope and how and in what way they address the identified themes and list as many technologies as you want			
No	Category	Technology Name	Short Description
1			
2			
3			
4			
...			
Question 2: Select the main features for identified technologies. Please add other features if required			
<i>Technology Name</i>			
A/I Machine learning Activity Dashboard Alerts / Notifications Application security Anomaly / Malware Detection Behavioural analysis Continuous monitoring Data Visualization Endpoint Detection and Response Event Analysis Fraud Detection Incident Management IOC verification Investigation Management Monitoring Network Monitoring Network provisioning Prioritization Real time data Remediation Management Reporting / Analytics Root cause analysis			

<p>Search / Filter Server Monitoring Task Management Threat Intelligence Threat Response Tokenization Vulnerability scanning Web-application security Whitelisting / blacklisting Others (please specify)</p>
<p>Question 3: Select the deployment option for identified technologies</p>
<p><i>Technology Name</i></p> <p>Cloud SaaS, Web based Desktop Mac Desktop Windows Desktop Linux On-Promise Windows On-Promise Linux Desktop Cromebook Mobile Android Mobile iPhone Mobile iPad Other (please specify....)</p>
<p>Question 4: Select the pricing option for identified technologies</p>
<p><i>Technology Name</i></p> <p>Free Free Trial Monthly subscription Annual Subscription One time license Other (please specify, example non-commercial Intellectual Property (IP))</p>
<p>Question 5: Select the availability mode of identified technologies</p>
<p><i>Technology Name</i></p> <p>Commercial Open source Non commercial Intellectual property (IP) (Originally developed by a university, research facility, or national laboratory, the tool is not available yet for purchase, licensing, or via opensource markets.)</p>
<p>Question 6: For non-commercial IP, select the technology readiness level and development timeline:</p> <p>Technology Readiness Level (TRL) Level 1 – Basic principles observed Level 2 – Technology concept formulated Level 3 – Experimental proof of concept Level 4 – Technology validated in lab Level 5 – Technology validated in relevant environment Level 6 – Technology demonstrated in relevant environment Level 7 – System prototype demonstration in operational environment</p>

Level 8 – System complete and qualified
 Level 9 – Actual system proven in operational environment

Development Timeline
 6 – 12 months
 1 – 2 years
 2-5 years
 More than 5 years

No	Technology / tool	TRL	Development timeline
1			
2			
3			
4			
5			
...			

Question 7: Is your company happy to demonstrate identified technologies and participate in live exercises with project's stakeholders?

Yes No

Appendix IV: Universities and research facilities questionnaire

General Information			
<i>University / Research Facility Name:</i>			
<i>Location:</i>			
<i>Name of person filling the survey:</i>			
<i>Role within the university / research facility:</i>			
<i>E-mail Address:</i>			
<i>Contact number:</i>			
Question 1: What are the <u>technologies/tools</u> that you are currently researching and/or developing in the domain of / related to (THEME X, Y or Z)?			
Select/ define category: Case Management Cyber Security Digital Forensics Threat Intelligence Other (specify)			
Please feel free to provide a short description technologies including their scope and how and in what way they address the identified themes and list as many technologies as you want			
No	Category	Technology/Tool Name	Short Description
1			
2			
3			
4			
...			
Question 2: Select the main features for technologies being researched or developed. Please add other features if required			
<i>Technology Name</i>			
A/I Machine learning Activity Dashboard Alerts / Notifications Application security Anomaly / Malware Detection Behavioural analysis Continuous monitoring Data Visualization Endpoint Detection and Response Event Analysis Fraud Detection Incident Management IOC verification Investigation Management Monitoring Network Monitoring Network provisioning Prioritization Real time data Remediation Management Reporting / Analytics Root cause analysis Search / Filter Server Monitoring			

- Task Management
- Threat Intelligence
- Threat Response
- Tokenization
- Vulnerability scanning
- Web-application security
- Whitelisting / blacklisting
- Others (please specify

Question 3: Select the deployment option for identified technologies – if known

Technology Name

- Cloud SaaS, Web based
- Desktop Mac
- Desktop Windows
- Desktop Linux
- On-Promise Windows
- On-Promise Linux
- Desktop Chromebook
- Mobile Android
- Mobile iPhone
- Mobile iPad
- Other (please specify.....)

Question 4: Select the technology readiness level:

Technology Readiness Level (TRL)

- Level 1 – Basic principles observed
- Level 2 – Technology concept formulated
- Level 3 – Experimental proof of concept
- Level 4 – Technology validated in lab
- Level 5 – Technology validated in relevant environment
- Level 6 – Technology demonstrated in relevant environment
- Level 7 – System prototype demonstration in operational environment
- Level 8 – System complete and qualified
- Level 9 – Actual system proven in operational environment

No	Technology Name	Technology Readiness Level
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		
...		

Question 5: Select the technology development timeline (when the technology will be ready to use)

- 6 – 12 months
- 1 – 2 years
- 2-5 years
- More than 5 years

No	Technology Name	Development Timeline
1		
2		

3
4
5
...
Question 6: Is your organisation happy to demonstrate identified R&D technologies and participate in live exercises with project's stakeholders
Yes No

Appendix V: Security networks and relevant stakeholders' questionnaire

General Information			
<i>Organization Name:</i>			
<i>Location:</i>			
<i>Main domains the organization focuses on:</i>			
<i>Name of person filling the survey:</i>			
<i>Role within the organization:</i>			
<i>E-mail Address:</i>			
<i>Contact number:</i>			
Question 1: What are the technologies/tools that you recommend OR R&D technologies that you are aware of that focus on (THEME X, Y or Z)?			
Select/ define category: Case Management Cyber Security Digital Forensics Threat Intelligence Other (specify)			
Please provide a short description technologies including their scope and how and in what way they address the identified themes and list as many technologies as you want			
No	Category	Technology Name	Short Description
1			
2			
3			
4			
...			
Question 2: Select the main features for identified technologies. Please add other features if required			
<i>Technology Name</i>			
A/I Machine learning Activity Dashboard Alerts / Notifications Application security Anomaly / Malware Detection Behavioural analysis Continuous monitoring Data Visualization Endpoint Detection and Response Event Analysis Fraud Detection Incident Management IOC verification Investigation Management Monitoring Network Monitoring Network provisioning Prioritization Real time data Remediation Management Reporting / Analytics Root cause analysis			

Search / Filter Server Monitoring Task Management Threat Intelligence Threat Response Tokenization Vulnerability scanning Web-application security Whitelisting / blacklisting Others (please specify)
Question 3: Select the deployment option for identified technologies
<i>Technology Name</i>
Cloud SaaS, Web based Desktop Mac Desktop Windows Desktop Linux On-Promise Windows On-Promise Linux Desktop Cromebook Mobile Android Mobile iPhone Mobile iPad Others (please specify.....)
Question 4: Select the pricing option for identified technologies
<i>Technology Name</i>
Free Free Trial Monthly subscription Annual Subscription One time license Other (please specify, example non-commercial Intellectual Property (IP))
Question 5: Select the availability mode of identified technologies
<i>Technology Name</i>
Commercial Open source Non-commercial Intellectual property (IP) (Originally developed by a university, research facility, or national laboratory, the tool is not available yet for purchase, licensing, or via opensource markets.)
Question 6: For non-commercial IP, select the technology readiness level and development timeline: Technology Readiness Level (TRL) Level 1 – Basic principles observed Level 2 – Technology concept formulated Level 3 – Experimental proof of concept Level 4 – Technology validated in lab Level 5 – Technology validated in relevant environment Level 6 – Technology demonstrated in relevant environment Level 7 – System prototype demonstration in operational environment Level 8 – System complete and qualified

Level 9 – Actual system proven in operational environment	
Development Timeline	
6 – 12 months	
1 – 2 years	
2-5 years	
More than 5 years	
No	Technology / tool Technology Readiness Level (TRL) Development timeline
1	
2	
3	
4	
5	
...	

Appendix VI: Live Exercise Evaluation Form

This questionnaire is to collect information on your experience with the solution used/expermiented during the live exercicies.

LEA Name

Practitioner name (optional):

Role within the LEA):

Investigator Digital Forensic expert First Responder Prosecutor
 Others (please specify)

Domain / Specialty:

Please specify specialties / domains under selected role

Venue and date of live exercise:

Solution name / Scenario number:

	QUESTION	RESPONSE (PLEASE SELECT ONE OPTION AND ADD ANY ADDITIONAL FEEDBACK YOU HAVE UNDER OTHER COMMENTS)				
A.	Process: did the live exercise allow sufficient time to test and validate the solution?	Highly inadequate	Inadequate	Borderline	Sufficient	Generous
B.	Process: did you believe the live exercise gave an accurate view of the solution?	Very poor	Inadequate	Adequate	Good	Excellent
C.	Solution: what is your view on the <i>capability</i> of the solution?	Clearly inadequate	Marginal	Acceptable	Good	Excellent
D.	Solution: what is your view on the <i>interoperability</i> of the solution within your working environment?	Very poor	Inadequate	Adequate	Good	Excellent
E.	Solution: what is your view on the <i>maturity</i> of the solution?	Clearly inadequate	Marginal	Acceptable	Good	Excellent

F.	Solution: what is your initial view on the <i>usability</i> ('friendliness') of the solution?	Clearly inadequate	Marginal	Acceptable	Good	Excellent
G.	Opinion on suitability: to what extent this solution meets your requirements as an <i>individual noting your role?</i>	Clearly unsuitable	Marginal	Acceptable	Good	Excellent
H.	Opinion on suitability: to what extent this solution meets your requirements as an <i>organization?</i>	Clearly unsuitable	Marginal	Acceptable	Good	Excellent
I.	Other Comments					

Remediation Management Reporting / Analytics Root cause analysis Search / Filter Server Monitoring Task Management Threat Intelligence Threat Response Tokenization Vulnerability scanning Web-application security Whitelisting / blacklisting Others (please specify and/or add any further explanation you like.....)
Question 3: Select additional / new deployment options of identified technologies / R&D initiatives demonstrated during the past joint live exercises (if exist)
<i>Technology Name</i>
Cloud SaaS, Web based Desktop Mac Desktop Windows Desktop Linux On-Promise Windows On-Promise Linux Desktop Cromebook Mobile Android Mobile iPhone Mobile iPad Others (please specify and/or add any further explanation you like.....)
Question 4: Select any new pricing option for identified technologies/R&D innovations (if now available)
<i>Technology Name</i>
Free Free Trial Monthly subscription Annual Subscription One time license Other (please specify and/or add any further explanation you like.....)
Question 5: Select the availability mode of identified technologies / R&D Innovations demonstrated during the past joint live exercises
<i>Technology Name</i>
Commercial Open source Non-commercial Intellectual property (IP) (Originally developed by a university, research facility, or national laboratory, the tool is not available yet for purchase, licensing, or via opensource markets.) (Please add any further explanation you like.....)
Question 6: <u>For non-commercial IP</u>, select the technology readiness level and development timeline of demonstrated technologies during the past joint live exercises: Technology Readiness Level (TRL) Level 1 – Basic principles observed Level 2 – Technology concept formulated

- Level 3 – Experimental proof of concept
- Level 4 – Technology validated in lab
- Level 5 – Technology validated in relevant environment
- Level 6 – Technology demonstrated in relevant environment
- Level 7 – System prototype demonstration in operational environment
- Level 8 – System complete and qualified
- Level 9 – Actual system proven in operational environment

Development Timeline

- 6 – 12 months
- 1 – 2 years
- 2-5 years
- More than 5 years

(please add any further explanation you like)

No	Technology / tool	TRL	Dev. Timeline	Further Details
1				
2				
3				
4				
5				
...				

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